

The more knowledge, the more grief: Auditing how search engine algorithms structure memories about mass atrocities

In today's algorithm-driven media ecologies, search engines such as Google or Baidu serve as key modulators of public knowledge about the present and the past. Using big data and machine learning techniques, search algorithms allow users to tackle the information overload by filtering, ranking and personalizing information in response to their queries. However, by doing so, search engines become hegemonic gate-keepers determining what information is consumed by the citizens (Noble 2018).

With a few exceptions (e.g. Hitchcock 2013; Pfanzelter 2015; Zavadski & Toepfl 2019), there is still limited research on how search engines structure historical knowledge. Yet, this question is of paramount importance considering the ongoing "algorithmic" (Esposito 2017) memory turn, under which collective perceptions of the past are increasingly shaped by search algorithms. By deciding what kind of sources to promote and whether to give visibility to revisionist/negationist narratives, search engines create hierarchies of historical knowledge. Similarly, the prioritization of specific pieces of (audio)visual content has significant implications for the cultural lexicon of symbols used to represent the past (Stier 2015).

In our paper, we introduce a novel approach for large-scale comparative analysis of algorithmic structuring of historical knowledge. Building upon earlier studies on algorithmic auditing (e.g. Hannák et al. 2017; Kulshrestha et al. 2017; Puschmann 2019; Makhortykh et al. 2020), we develop a distributed cloud-based research infrastructure for emulating and recording the browsing behaviour of multiple autonomous agents. Each agent is deployed in a desktop browser (for the current study we used Chrome and Firefox browsers), where two extensions (a bot and a tracker) are installed. The bot emulates user browsing behavior by searching terms from a pre-defined list and then navigates through the search results. The tracker collects the HTML from each page visited by the bot and sends it to a storage server. This approach enables more control over specific variables (e.g. browser type, browser history or time when the search is initialized) and allows identifying the effect of different factors on how memory-related content is structured and prioritized.

As a case study, we looked at how memory of three cases of mass atrocities committed in the 20th century - the Armenian Genocide, the Holodomor and the Holocaust - is structured in six major search engines, i.e Google, Yandex, Bing, Yahoo, DuckDuckGo and Baidu. Using queries in English, Russian and Mandarin Chinese (the selection of languages is attributed to the affiliation of corporations behind the search engines; the specific queries were "holocaust", "holodomor", and "armenian genocide" in the three respective languages) and a large number of autonomous agents (n=200), we collected for each agent the first 50 search results together with the first 50 images and the 50 videos suggested by a specific search engine in relation to the three events. While doing so, we took several measures to isolate the effect of search personalization; specifically, we used dynamic cloud-based IPs for each agent, synchronised their activity to isolate the factor of time and compared it across two browsers (Chrome and Firefox).

Using the collected data, we then discuss the following questions: In which ways do the hierarchies of historical sources differ between the search engines and how are these hierarchies affected by the language of the query and/or external variables (e.g. browser type)? How significant is the effect

of randomization on the ranking of atrocities-related content within a specific search engine and what are the consequences for knowledge structuring? How different is prioritization of (audio)visual representations of the mass atrocities between the search engines and what aspects of the events are promoted by these algorithmically “iconized” images?

Currently, the paper is in the analysis stage: the data are collected and the first round of quantitative analysis for Holocaust-related text queries in English is completed. Based on Jaccard coefficient and rank biased overlap (Webber et al. 2010), we identified significant differences in the ways search engines select and rank historical sources. These observations are supported by the first round of content analysis, for which we coded the type of sources prioritized by the search engines. As shown by Fig. 1, there are significant differences in the composition of hierarchies of the Holocaust-related knowledge with some search engines prioritizing Holocaust-related content coming online encyclopedias (Yahoo and Yandex) and others giving priority to recent updates related to the Holocaust remembrance (Bing and Google). In the case of the largest Russian search engine, Yandex, we also observed the presence of references to the Holocaust denial websites in the top 10 search results.

Fig. 1. Top 10 resources in relation to the Holocaust by the engine

In the follow-up studies, we anticipate to compare the results for English queries with the results for the queries in two other languages. We are also going to address the major limitation of the current work - i.e., it being a snapshot experiment - and look at how consistent are the observed differences between the search engines. To do so, a more longitudinal study will be required similar to the one conducted by Zavadski & Toepfl (2019) in their research on how search engines mediate historical events in the Russian context.

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